

**THE ODD/EVEN DICHOTOMY FOR THE SET OF NUMBERS
THAT ARE BOTH k -FULL AND ℓ -FREE**

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Abstract

A $[k, \ell]$ -integer is a natural number that is both k -full and ℓ -free. Using an elementary method, an asymptotic ratio of the set of odd $[k, \ell]$ -integers to that of even $[k, \ell]$ -integer is derived.

1. Introduction and Results

Let k and ℓ be two fixed integers such that $2 \leq k < \ell$. A natural number n is called ℓ -free if for all primes p dividing n , we have that p^ℓ does not divide n . A natural number n is called k -full if for all primes p dividing n , we have $p^k \mid n$. A natural number $n_{k,\ell}$ is called $[k, \ell]$ -integer if for all primes p dividing n , we have $p^k \mid n$ but $p^\ell \nmid n$. Let $N_{k,\ell}$ denote the set of all $[k, \ell]$ -integers, and let $N_{k,\ell}(x)$ denote the number of integers that are in $N_{k,\ell}$ and that do not exceed x . In 1995, Krätzel [5] and Seibold [9] studied the asymptotic behavior of $N_{k,\ell}(x)$ and showed that

$$N_{k,\ell}(x) = \sum_{n=k}^{\min\{2k,\ell\}-1} c_{k,\ell}^{(n)} x^{1/n} + \Delta(x), \quad (1)$$

where

$$c_{k,\ell}^{(n)} = \operatorname{Res}_{s=1/n} \frac{F_{k,\ell}(s)}{s}, \quad F_{k,\ell}(s) = \prod_p \left(1 + \sum_{v=k}^{\ell-1} p^{-vs} \right),$$

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and $\Delta(x)$ is the error term. The distribution of these numbers $n_{k,\ell}$ attracted the attention of many authors; see [5, 6, 9, 11, 12, 13].

In 2008 Scott [8] conjectured that one third of the square-free numbers are even and this was proven by Jameson in [3]. He proved that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S_o(x)}{S_e(x)} = 2, \tag{2}$$

where $S_o(x)$ and $S_e(x)$ denote the number of all odd and even square-free numbers that do not exceed x , respectively. In 2020 Srichan [10] used an elementary method to prove that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_o(x)}{N_e(x)} = 2 - \sqrt{2}, \tag{3}$$

where $N_o(x)$ and $N_e(x)$ denote the number of all odd and even square-full numbers that do not exceed x , respectively. One year later, Puttasontiphot and Srichan [7] considered this for the case of cube-full numbers and proved that,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{C_o(x)}{C_e(x)} = 2 - 2^{2/3}, \tag{4}$$

where $C_o(x)$ and $C_e(x)$ denote the number of all odd and even cube-full numbers that do not exceed x , respectively. In 2021, Jameson [4] reproved his result in [3] by using the same method as in [10]. Thus, it is interesting to use the elementary method in [10] to generalize this to the case of $[k, \ell]$ -integers.

We will use the following notation. For a given set \mathcal{A} and $x > 1$, $\mathcal{A}(x)$ denotes the number of elements in \mathcal{A} that do not exceed x . Here, for two fixed integers k and ℓ such that $2 \leq k < \ell < \infty$, we denote by $O_{k,\ell}$ and $E_{k,\ell}$ the set of all odd and even $[k, \ell]$ -integers, respectively. The symbol $f(x) \sim g(x)$ means $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} = 1$, and we say that $f(x)$ is asymptotic to $g(x)$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$. The notation $[x]$ denotes the greatest integer not exceeding real x .

Here we prove the following results.

Theorem 1. *As $x \rightarrow \infty$, we have*

$$\frac{O_{k,\ell}(x)}{E_{k,\ell}(x)} \sim \frac{2 - 2^{1-(1/k)}}{1 - 2^{1-(\ell/k)}}.$$

Should the preceding definition and notation be allowed for $k = 1$, then 1-full numbers are merely positive integers and generalized ℓ -free integers are just $[1, \ell]$ -integers. The following corollary generalizes (2).

Corollary 1. *As $x \rightarrow \infty$, we have*

$$\frac{O_{1,\ell}(x)}{E_{1,\ell}(x)} \sim \frac{2^\ell}{2^\ell - 2}.$$

Moreover, we note that, for x large enough and $2 \leq k < x$, all $[k, \lfloor x \rfloor]$ -integers not exceeding x are k -full integers. Thus, Theorem 1 recovers (3) and (4). Namely, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 2. *As $x \rightarrow \infty$, we have*

$$\frac{O_{k, \lfloor x \rfloor}(x)}{E_{k, \lfloor x \rfloor}(x)} = \frac{K_o(x)}{K_e(x)} \sim 2 - 2^{1-(1/k)},$$

where $K_o(x)$ and $K_e(x)$ denote the number of all odd and even k -full numbers that do not exceed x , respectively.

Proof. This follows immediately from the fact that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{2 - 2^{1-(1/k)}}{1 - 2^{1-(\lfloor x \rfloor/k)}} = 2 - 2^{1-(1/k)}.$$

□

2. Proof of Theorem 1

We now prove Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. Let k and ℓ be two fixed integers such that $2 \leq k < \ell$. Recall that $N_{k, \ell}$ denotes the set of all $[k, \ell]$ -integers and $O_{k, \ell}$ and $E_{k, \ell}$ denote the set of all odd and even $[k, \ell]$ -integers, respectively. Assume that, as $x \rightarrow \infty$,

$$O_{k, \ell}(x) \sim ax^{1/k} \quad \text{and} \quad E_{k, \ell}(x) \sim bx^{1/k}, \quad \text{for some } a, b \in \mathbb{R}^+. \quad (5)$$

We will show that, as $x \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\frac{a}{b} = \frac{2 - 2^{1-(1/k)}}{1 - 2^{1-(\ell/k)}}. \quad (6)$$

For $0 \leq i \leq \ell - k - 1$, we define $\mathcal{A}_i = \{n \in E_{k, \ell} : n = 2^{k+i}m, m \in O_{k, \ell}\}$. By this definition, we have $\mathcal{A}_i(x) = O_{k, \ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{k+i}}\right)$, for $0 \leq i \leq \ell - k - 1$. Thus, we have

$$E_{k, \ell}(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k, \ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{k+i}}\right). \quad (7)$$

In view of (5) and (7), we have

$$bx^{1/k} = \sum_{i=0}^{\ell-k-1} a \left(\frac{x}{2^{k+i}}\right)^{1/k}.$$

This proves (6).

Now it remains to prove the existence of a and b . In view of (7), we write

$$N_{k,\ell}(x) = O_{k,\ell}(x) + E_{k,\ell}(x) = O_{k,\ell}(x) + \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{k+i_1}}\right). \tag{8}$$

For $0 \leq i_2 \leq \ell - k - 1$, we replace x in (8) by $\frac{x}{2^{k+i_2}}$ and then sum that equation over all i_2 . Thus,

$$\sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} N_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{k+i_2}}\right) = \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{k+i_2}}\right) + \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{2k+i_1+i_2}}\right). \tag{9}$$

In view of (8) and (9), we have

$$N_{k,\ell}(x) - \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} N_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{k+i_2}}\right) = O_{k,\ell}(x) - \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{2k+i_1+i_2}}\right). \tag{10}$$

We redo this process and get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} N_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{2k+i_1+i_2}}\right) &= \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{2k+i_1+i_2}}\right) \\ &+ \sum_{i_3=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{3k+i_1+i_2+i_3}}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

In view of (10) and (11), we have

$$\begin{aligned} N_{k,\ell}(x) - \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} N_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{k+i_2}}\right) &+ \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} N_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{2k+i_1+i_2}}\right) \\ &= O_{k,\ell}(x) + \sum_{i_3=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{3k+i_1+i_2+i_3}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Repeating this, we have, for $v \geq 2$,

$$\begin{aligned} N_{k,\ell}(x) - \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} N_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{k+i_1}}\right) &+ \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} N_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{2k+i_1+i_2}}\right) + \dots \\ &+ \dots + (-1)^v \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \dots \sum_{i_v=0}^{\ell-k-1} N_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{vk+i_1+i_2+\dots+i_v}}\right) \\ &= O_{k,\ell}(x) + (-1)^v \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \dots \sum_{i_{v+1}=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell}\left(\frac{x}{2^{(v+1)k+i_1+i_2+\dots+i_{v+1}}}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

In view of (1), we have $N_{k,\ell}(x) \sim cx^{1/k}$ for some $c \in \mathbb{R}^+$. For $\epsilon > 0$, we take x_0 such that $(c - \epsilon)x^{1/k} \leq N_{k,\ell}(x) \leq (c + \epsilon)x^{1/k}$, for all $x > x_0$. For $x > x_0$, we choose an odd positive integer v such that $x_0^k > \frac{x}{2^{v(k-1)}}$ and $x_0 < \frac{x}{2^{(\ell-1)v}}$. From (12), we have, for $x > x_0 2^{(\ell-1)v}$,

$$\begin{aligned} O_{k,\ell}(x) &\geq (c - \epsilon)x^{1/k} - (c + \epsilon)x^{1/k} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^{k+i_1}}\right)^{1/k} \\ &\quad + (c - \epsilon)x^{1/k} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^{2k+i_1+i_2}}\right)^{1/k} + \dots \\ &\quad - (c + \epsilon)x^{1/k} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \dots \sum_{i_v=0}^{\ell-k-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^{vk+i_1+i_2+\dots+i_v}}\right)^{1/k} \\ &\quad + \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \dots \sum_{i_{v+1}=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell} \left(\frac{x}{2^{(v+1)k+i_1+i_2+\dots+i_{v+1}}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

From the fact that $O_{k,\ell}(x) \geq 0$ for all $x > 0$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} O_{k,\ell}(x) &\geq (c - \epsilon)x^{1/k} - (c + \epsilon)x^{1/k} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^{k+i_1}}\right)^{1/k} \\ &\quad + (c - \epsilon)x^{1/k} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^{2k+i_1+i_2}}\right)^{1/k} + \dots \\ &\quad - (c + \epsilon)x^{1/k} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \dots \sum_{i_v=0}^{\ell-k-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^{vk+i_1+i_2+\dots+i_v}}\right)^{1/k} \\ &= \left(c \left(\frac{1 + \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 + \frac{A}{2}}\right) - \epsilon \left(\frac{1 - \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 - \frac{A}{2}}\right)\right) x^{1/k}, \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where $A = \sum_{i=0}^{\ell-k-1} 2^{-i/k}$. Now we consider the upper bound of $O_{k,\ell}(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} O_{k,\ell}(x) &\leq (c + \epsilon)x^{1/k} - (c - \epsilon)x^{1/k} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^{k+i_1}}\right)^{1/k} \\ &\quad + (c + \epsilon)x^{1/k} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{\ell-k-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^{2k+i_1+i_2}}\right)^{1/k} + \dots \\ &\quad - (c - \epsilon)x^{1/k} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \dots \sum_{i_v=0}^{\ell-k-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^{vk+i_1+i_2+\dots+i_v}}\right)^{1/k} \\ &\quad + \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \dots \sum_{i_{v+1}=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell} \left(\frac{x}{2^{(v+1)k+i_1+i_2+\dots+i_{v+1}}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
 O_{k,\ell}(x) &\leq \left(c \left(\frac{1 + \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 + \frac{A}{2}} \right) + \epsilon \left(\frac{1 - \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 - \frac{A}{2}} \right) \right) x^{1/k} \\
 &\quad + \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \cdots \sum_{i_{v+1}=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell} \left(\frac{x}{2^{(v+1)k+i_1+i_2+\cdots+i_{v+1}}} \right). \tag{14}
 \end{aligned}$$

From (7) and choosing v such that $x_0^k > \frac{x}{2^{v(k-1)}}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \cdots \sum_{i_v=0}^{\ell-k-1} O_{k,\ell} \left(\frac{x}{2^{vk+k+i_1+\cdots+i_v}} \right) &= \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \cdots \sum_{i_v=0}^{\ell-k-1} E_{k,\ell} \left(\frac{x}{2^{(v+1)k+i_1+\cdots+i_v}} \right) \\
 &< \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \cdots \sum_{i_v=0}^{\ell-k-1} \frac{x}{2^{vk+i_1+\cdots+i_v}} \\
 &< \frac{x_0^k}{2^v} \sum_{i_1=0}^{\ell-k-1} \cdots \sum_{i_v=0}^{\ell-k-1} \frac{1}{2^{i_1+\cdots+i_v}} \\
 &= \frac{x_0^k}{2^v} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{\ell-k-1} \frac{1}{2^i} \right)^v \\
 &< x_0^k \\
 &< x_0^k \left(\frac{1 - \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 - \frac{A}{2}} \right). \tag{15}
 \end{aligned}$$

In view of (14) and (15), we have, for $x > \frac{x_0^{k^2}}{\epsilon^k}$,

$$O_{k,\ell}(x) \leq \left(c \left(\frac{1 + \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 + \frac{A}{2}} \right) + 2\epsilon \left(\frac{1 - \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 - \frac{A}{2}} \right) \right) x^{1/k}. \tag{16}$$

From (13) and (16), we have

$$\left(c \left(\frac{1 + \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 + \frac{A}{2}} \right) - \epsilon \left(\frac{1 - \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 - \frac{A}{2}} \right) \right) x^{1/k} \leq O_{k,\ell}(x) \leq \left(c \left(\frac{1 + \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 + \frac{A}{2}} \right) + 2\epsilon \left(\frac{1 - \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^{v+1}}{1 - \frac{A}{2}} \right) \right) x^{1/k}.$$

This inequality proves the existence of a and from (8) the existence of b follows from the existence a . □

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